

**QBD BASED STABILITY INDICATING RP-HPLC METHOD FOR COMBINED
ANTIRETROVIRAL TABLETS**

Sridevi Pulakanam^{1*}, Kumbha Prathyusha², Mule Venkatachennakesavareddy³, Mangalapudi Rami Reddy⁴,
Maruprolu Anil Kumar Reddy⁵

^{1,2}Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry and Analysis, Bapatla College of Pharmacy, Bapatla -522101, Andhra Pradesh, India.

^{3,4,5}Final Year Student of Bapatla College of Pharmacy, Bapatla -522101, Andhra Pradesh, India.

*Corresponding Author: Sridevi Pulakanam

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ABSTRACT

A tablet containing Dolutegravir, Lamivudine, and Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate is a combined drug of antiretroviral medication used to treat HIV/AIDS. WHO recognised this drug as the first-line treatment for adults. The primary purpose of this study is to develop and validate a simple, accurate, precise, and reproducible reverse-phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) method for estimating dolutegravir, Lamivudine, and Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate in bulk and tablet dosage forms by optimising chromatographic parameters using a two-level full factorial design. A 2-level full factorial design was utilised to optimise the type of column and percentage of organic phase to maximise the theoretical plates and minimise the retention time of all three drugs. The optimised strength of acetonitrile and 1% ortho phosphoric acid buffer (70:30), flow rate and the volume of injection were found to be 1ml/min and 20 µl, respectively. The retention times were found to be 3.785min, 1.529min and 3.140 min for Dolutegravir, Lamivudine and Tenofovir, respectively. The R² values for Dolutegravir, Lamivudine and Tenofovir were found to be 0.99985, 0.99994 and 0.99923, respectively. The theoretical plate number and tailing factor for Dolutegravir, Lamivudine and Tenofovir were found to be NLT 2000 and should not be more than 2, respectively. The per cent RSD of peak areas of all measurements was found to be less than 2.0. The QBD approach was found to be an effective technique for optimising chromatographic conditions of the proposed method, which is useful for routine analysis of Dolutegravir, Lamivudine, and Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate in pharmaceutical dosage form.

KEYWORDS: RP-HPLC, Dolutegravir, Lamivudine, Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate, Qbd, ICH guidelines.

1. INTRODUCTION

Antiretroviral therapy (ART)^[1] has significantly evolved over the last few decades since the development of the first nucleoside analogues NRTIS^[2] (nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitors). With the advent of triple therapy, majority of the challenges has been resolved. The latest class of the antiretroviral drugs developed was integrase inhibitors (INI).^[3] Dolutegravir^[4], (3S,7R)-N-[(2,4-difluorophenyl)methyl]-11-hydroxy-7-methyl-9,12-dioxo-4-oxa-1,8-diazatricyclo[8.4.0.0^{3,8}]{3,8}tetradeca-10,13-diene-13-carboxamide^[5] is an integrase inhibitor. It blocks HIV integrase enzyme by binding to the active site and obstructing the strand transfer step which is

important in the HIV replication cycle and leads to the inhibition of viral activity.

Fig. 1: Dolutegravir.

Lamivudine^[6] is 2,4-amino-1-[(2R,5S)-2-(hydroxymethyl)-1,3-oxathiolan-5-yl]-1,2-dihydropyrimidin-2-one.^[7] It has a structural similarity with cytosine. It can inhibit both HIV -1 & 2 reverse transcriptase and the reverse transcriptase of hepatitis B virus. The phosphorylated active metabolite competes for incorporation into viral DNA.

Fig. 2: Lamivudine.

Tenofovir^[8-9] disoproxil Fumarate, 2E)-but-2-enedioic acid; bis({[(propan-2-yl)oxy]carbonyl}oxy)methyl} {[(2R)-1-(6-amino-9H-purin-9-yl)propan-2-yl]oxy}methanephosphonate.^[10] Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate is hydrolyzed to Tenofovir, which is then phosphorylated to Tenofovir diphosphate. Tenofovir diphosphate inhibits the activity of HIV-1 reverse transcriptase by competing with the natural substrate, deoxy adenosine 5'-triphosphate, and by DNA chain termination.

Fig. 3: Tenofovir.

Upon the literature survey there were many analytical methods have been reported individually or in combination with other drugs.^[11-19] However, there is no method reported for the simultaneous estimation of these three drugs by the HPLC method. Hence, the authors attempted to develop a stability indicating RP-HPLC method^[20-25] for simultaneous estimation of drugs using QBD approach^[26-36] to reduce no. of trials, cost and time.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Apparatus and Equipment

- HPLC studies were carried out on ALLIANCE Waters e 2695, Empower software 2.0 version, with a PDA detector set at 250nm for UV detection

- Waters Symmetry C18 (150 x 4.6mm) 3.5 μ , X-Bridge Phenyl (150 x 4.6mm) 3.5 μ , columns were utilised in the study.
- Statistical software tool like Minitab version 16.2.3 tab for DOE,
- pH meter – Eutech was used to check pH of all solutions.
- Other equipment like weighing balance – Sartorius,
- UV/VIS spectrophotometer SHIMADZU UV-1700 5, Ultra sonicator UCA 701 Unichrome.

2.2. Chemicals and Reagents

- Acetonitrile (HPLC grade)
- Ortho phosphoric acid (HPLC grade)
- Methanol (HPLC grade)
- HPLC grade water (Milli Q or equivalent)

Dolutegravir, lamivudine and tenofovir were gift samples obtained from Aurobindo Pharmaceuticals Ltd., Hyderabad. Tablets of Virophil (dolutegravir-50 mg, lamivudine-300 mg and tenofovir disoproxil fumarate-300mg) were purchased from a local pharmacy store.

2.3. Method development

2.3.1. Determination of Working Wavelength (λ_{max})

The λ_{max} of the solution of the drugs in a mixture of acetonitrile and 0.1% v/v OPA (50:50) was determined within the wavelength region of 200–400 nm against the same mixture as a blank. Thus, the isobestic point of two drugs at 250 nm was selected as the wavelength for further development of the method.

2.3.2. Initial Chromatographic Conditions

Different reverse-phase columns, as well as various organic solvents, such as OPA buffer and acetonitrile, were used to test the procedure at first. All the trials, observations and remarks were shown in Table 1. Ultimately, a sufficient separation was carried out on X-Bridge Phenyl (150X4.6mm) 3.5 μ using a combination of 0.1% OPA and acetonitrile.

From the trials, as the type of column and percentage of organic phase brought about a large change in retention time and theoretical plates they were selected as two factors to create 2² full factorial design^[37-49] and for method development.

2.3.3. Preparation Of Standard Stock Solution

Weighed accurately and transferred 10 mg of Dolutegravir, 60 mg of Lamivudine and 60mg of Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate working standard into a 100 ml clean dried volumetric flask and 20 ml diluent was added, sonicated, and the final volume was made with the diluent. From the above stock solution, 5 ml was pipetted into a 50 ml volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluent (10ppm of Dolutegravir, 60ppm of Lamivudine and 60ppm of Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate).

2.3.4. Preparation of Sample Stock Solution

A total of 20 tablets were accurately weighed, and the average weight tablet was taken. 20 tablets were powdered, and an amount equivalent to 150 mg of tablet powder was accurately weighed into a clean, dried 100 ml volumetric flask. Diluent of 40 ml was added and sonicated for 20 mins, and volume was made up to the mark with the diluent. The solution was centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 10 mins, and 5ml of supernatant solution was pipeted into a 50 ml cleaned, dried volumetric flask and the final volume was made up with the diluent. Solution was passed through a 0.45-micron Millipore PVDF filter to get (10ppm of Dolutegravir, 60ppm of Lamivudine and 60ppm of Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate).

2.4. Optimisation of method

The QbD approach acknowledges dependent variables, independent variables and their interaction effects by a proper set of experiments on the responses to be

analysed. Full factorial design (FFD), is one of the QbD approaches, an effective tool and commonly used for statistical optimization and analysis in scientific research and industrial applications.

2.4.1. Selection of factors

In this study, two independent variables were identified, such as columns and % of organic phase, which needed to be controlled to achieve the acceptable response range of dependent variables, such as theoretical plates NMT 5000 and retention time less than 4 min, were taken to create a factorial design.

After defining the variables, the 2^2 full factorial design, one of the powerful software techniques of DoE [50 -56] was utilised to create a design by the input data of two factors as type of column (Waters & X-bridge) and % Organic phase at limits of (low-30 & high-70) as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Chromatographic conditions set for factorial design.

Factor	Name	Type	Low	High
A	Column	text	Waters	X-bridge
B	% organic phase	Numeric	30	70

2.4.2 Screening

In this step, the summary of the factorial design was generated by the response analyser, used for screening of

method variables and process parameters at their respective low and high levels and shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Summary of factorial design.

Std Order	Run Order	Center pt	Blocks	Column	%organic phase
1	1	1	1	Waters	30
4	2	1	1	X-bridge	70
8	3	1	1	X-bridge	70
6	4	1	1	X-bridge	30
2	5	1	1	X-bridge	30
7	6	1	1	Waters	70
5	7	1	1	Waters	30
3	8	1	1	Waters	70

The above table gives the summary of the design matrix as per the Full Factorial Design, showing Two-Factor Eight-Experimental runs along with duplicate studies of centre point (1, 1) runs.

With a small number of trials, the DOE of Minitab (version 16.2.3) was used to explore the effect of a variety of conditions on a specific response as well as their interactions. The generated data was analysed and found that the type of column and % organic phase had shown significant p values computed in ANOVA [57 – 63] and shown in Table 4 –9.

A desirability function was applied to the optimised conditions by setting a target ranging from 4100-5400 for theoretical plates and 1.4-3.7 minutes for retention time. This desirability was studied on a scale that ranges from d=0 to d=1 for undesirable and fully desirable responses, respectively, for theoretical plates and

retention time. The optimum conditions with desired target points as shown in the opti plot. (Fig. 5). To finalise this optimum set of conditions, three replicate injections of 50 µg/ml of dolutegravir, 300µg/ml of lamivudine and 300µg/ml of tenofovir disoproxil fumarate were analysed to determine their observed retention time of all three drugs, resolution, asymmetry and theoretical plates were within the predicted ranges. It was calculated using formula of Relative error % and observed that the differences between the observed and predicted peak responses were less than 5%.

Relative error percentage = $\frac{\text{Predicted value} - \text{Experimental value}}{\text{Predicted value}} * 100$

2.4.3. Optimised chromatographic conditions

The optimised chromatographic conditions are shown in Table 10. The chromatogram is shown in Fig. 6.

Table 10: Optimised chromatographic conditions.

PARAMETERS	OBSERVATION
Instrument used	Waters HPLC with auto sampler and PDA detector.
Injection volume	10µl
Mobile Phase	Acetonitrile and 0.1% OPA(70:30)
Column	X-Bridge Phenyl (150x4.6mm) 3.5µ
Detection Wave Length	250 nm
Flow Rate	1 ml/min
Runtime	10min

2.5. Assay Procedure

The standard, a sample of 10 µl were injected into the chromatographic system and the areas for Lamivudine, Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate and Dolutegravir peaks

were measured, and % assay was calculated by using the formula, and the results were given in Table 11. and peaks were shown in (Fig. 7).

$$\% \text{ ASSAY} = \frac{\text{sample area response}}{\text{standard area response}} \times \frac{\text{standard weight}}{\text{standard dilution}} \times \frac{\text{sample dilution}}{\text{sample weight}} \times \frac{\text{potency}}{(100 - \text{water or LOD})} \times 100$$

2.6. Method validation

The validation was performed for the optimised chromatographic analytical method as per ICH Q2(R1)^[64-68] guidelines.

2.6.1. Linearity

The linearity was performed at six concentration levels, 1-15 µg/ml for dolutegravir, 6-90 µg/ml for lamivudine and 6-90 µg/ml for tenofovir, respectively, and plots were constructed for concentration against peak area. The results obtained were given in Table.12, and plots were shown in (Fig. 9-10).

2.6.2. Accuracy

Accuracy was carried out by adding a known amount of standard to the tablet solution for each drug at 50, 100, and 150 % levels in triplicate, and samples were analysed by the optimised method. The mean percentage recoveries were determined and given in Table 13-15. and chromatograms were shown in (Fig 11 - 13).

2.6.3. Precision

The samples of analytes were subjected to interday and intraday QC analyses for the determination of precision.

In method precision, each homogenous sample was analysed for 6 times.

The precision of the instrument was checked by injecting (n=6) solutions of 10ppm of

Dolutegravir, 60ppm of Lamivudine and 60ppm of Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate. In this % RSD was calculated for the peak areas obtained. The results were given in Table 16-17. and chromatograms were shown in (Fig. 14-15).

2.6.4. Robustness

The robustness of the method refers to its ability to remain unaffected by small and deliberate variations in method parameters. The robustness of the optimised method was investigated by injecting a standard solution

of 10ppm of Dolutegravir 60ppm of Lamivudine, and 60ppm of Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate with minute slight changes in the chromatographic parameters, flow rate (0.8 ml/min to 1.2ml/min), proportion of solvent in mobile phase (45:55) and results were shown in Table 18-20. Chromatograms were shown in (Fig. 16-19).

2.6.5. Limit of detection and Limit of quantification

LOD and LOQ for three drugs were evaluated using the standard deviation method. LOD was defined as 3.3 σ/S and LOQ as 10 σ/S based on the standard deviation of the response (σ) and slope of the calibration curve (S), and chromatograms were shown in (Fig. 20-21), and results were shown in Table 21.

2.6.6. System suitability

System suitability was checked by taking six replicates of three drugs at concentrations of 100 µg/ml. the retention time, theoretical plates, peak symmetry and %RSD of six injections were calculated, and the results are shown in Table 22.

Apart from applying the QbD approach to dosage forms, we aimed to investigate the stability of the drugs under the stress conditions with optimised conditions.

2.7. Forced degradation studies^[69-70]

Different stress conditions were applied to the samples, viz., acid, base, oxidative and thermal stress conditions separately and the solutions were analysed using HPLC.

2.7.1. Preparation of sample stock solution

20 tablets were weighed accurately, and the average weight was calculated. 20 tablets were powdered and 150 mg of equivalent tablet powder was accurately weighed into a clean, In a dried 100 ml volumetric flask, 40 ml of diluent was introduced, and the mixture was sonicated for 20 minutes with occasional shaking to ensure the contents dissolved. The solution was then topped up to the mark with the diluent. The solution was centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 10 mins. 5ml of supernatant solution was pipetted into a 50 ml cleaned, dried volumetric flask and

the final volume was made up to the mark with the diluent. The solution was filtered through a 0.45-micron Millipore PVDF filter.

2.7.2. Hydrolytic degradation under acidic conditions

5 ml of sample stock solution was pipetted into a 50 ml volumetric flask, and 3 ml of 1N HCl was added. Then, the volumetric flask was kept at 60°C for 6 hours and neutralised with 1 N NaOH and made up to 50 ml with diluent. The solution was filtered through a 0.45 micron Millipore PVDF filter. The chromatograms are shown in Fig. 22.

2.7.3. Hydrolytic degradation under alkaline conditions

Five millilitres of the aforementioned solution were transferred into a 50 ml volumetric flask, followed by the addition of 3 ml of 1N NaOH. The flask was then maintained at a temperature of 60°C for six hours. Afterwards, the solution was neutralised using 1N HCl and diluted to a total volume of 10 ml with a diluent. The

resulting solution was filtered through 0.22-micron syringe filters and subsequently transferred into vials. The chromatograms were shown in (Fig. 23).

2.7.4. Thermal-induced degradation

A Lamivudine sample was taken in petridish and kept in a hot air oven at 1100 C for 24 hours. Then the sample was taken, diluted with diluents and injected into the HPLC and analysed. The chromatograms are shown in (Fig. 24).

2.7.5. Oxidative degradation

5ml of the stock solution was pipetted into a 50 ml volumetric flask. Then, 1 ml of a 3% w/v hydrogen peroxide solution was added to the flask, and the volume was adjusted to the mark using a diluent. The flask was left at room temperature for 15 minutes. Afterwards, the solution was filtered through 0.45-micron syringe filters and transferred into vials. The chromatograms were shown in (Fig. 25).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Determination of Working Wavelength (λ_{max})

Fig. 4: Isobestic point of two drugs at 250 nm.

3.2. Method development by DOE

Table 1: Different trials with observations and remarks for method development.

Type of Column	Mobile phase composition	Observation	Remarks
Waters Symmetry C ₁₈ (150 x 4.6mm, 3.5 μ)	Acetonitrile and 0.1% OPA 60:40	Plate Count was not within the limit	Not satisfactory
	Acetonitrile and 0.1% OPA 30:70	The third peak was not eluted.	Not satisfactory
X-Bridge C ₈ (150 x 4.6mm, 3.5 μ)	Acetonitrile and 0.1% OPA 55:45	Only two peaks were eluted	Not satisfactory
	Acetonitrile and 0.1% OPA 60:40	Low plate count was observed	Not satisfactory
X-Bridge Phenyl C ₁₈ (150 x 4.6mm, 3.5 μ)	Acetonitrile and 0.1% OPA 50:50	Peak shapes were symmetrical with more no of theoretical plates.	Not Satisfactory
	Acetonitrile and 0.1% OPA 70:30	An unknown peak was formed at a 3.2 retention time	satisfactory

Table 4: Analysis of Variance for Theoretical plates of Lamivudine (coded units).

Source	DF	Seq SS	Adj SS	Adj MS	F	P
Main Effects	2	475033	475033	237516	8.20	0.038
column	1	431520	431520	431520	14.90	0.018
% organic phase	1	43513	43512	43512	1.50	0.287
2-Way Interactions	1	219122	219122	219122	7.57	0.051
column*solvent	1	219122	219122	219122	7.57	0.051
Residual Error	4	115829	115829	28957		
Pure Error	4	115829	115829	28957		
Total	7	809984				

The p-values for column and % organic phase obtained were 0.018, 0.287, not significant values predicts theoretical plates of lamivudine are independent of % organic phase and column.

Table 5: Analysis of Variance for Theoretical plates of tenofovir disoproxil fumarate (coded units).

Source	DF	Seq SS	Adj SS	Adj MS	F	P
Main Effects	2	784265	784265	392133	10.18	0.027
column	1	586445	586445	586445	15.23	0.018
% organic phase	1	197821	197821	197821	5.14	0.086
2-Way Interactions	1	140981	140981	140981	3.66	0.128
column*solvent	1	140981	140981	140981	3.66	0.128
Residual Error	4	154006	154006	38501		
Pure Error	4	154006	154006	38502		
Total	7	1079252				

The table showed that theoretical plates of tenofovir disoproxil fumarate are dependent on the column, as it shows p value<0.05.

Table 6: Analysis of Variance for Theoretical plates of dolutegravir (coded units).

Source	DF	Seq SS	Adj SS	Adj MS	F	P
Main Effects	2	5396841	5396841	2698421	112.22	0.000
column	1	3199185	3199185	3199185	133.04	0.000
% organic phase	1	2197656	2197656	2197656	91.39	0.001
2-Way Interactions	1	430128	430128	430128	17.89	0.013
column*solvent	1	430128	430128	430128	17.89	0.013
Residual Error	4	96188	96188	24047		
Pure Error	4	96188	96188	24047		
Total	7	5923157				

From the table, significant p-values were found. The response of theoretical plates is dependent on the % organic phase and the column.

Table 7: Analysis of Variance for Retention time of lamivudine (coded units).

Source	DF	Seq SS	Adj SS	Adj MS	F	P
Main Effects	2	15.2125	15.2125	7.6063	320.26	0.000
column	1	14.8513	14.8513	14.8513	625.32	0.000
% organic phase	1	0.3613	0.3613	0.3613	15.21	0.018
2-Way Interactions	1	0.0312	0.0312	0.0312	1.32	0.315
column*solvent	1	0.0312	0.0312	0.0312	1.32	0.315
Residual Error	4	0.0950	0.0950	0.0238		
Pure Error	4	0.0950	0.0950	0.0237		
Total	7	15.3388				

P= 0.000 for column and p=0.018 for % organic phase were obtained, and the retention time of lamivudine was found to be influenced by both factors.

Table 8: Analysis of Variance for Retention time of tenofovir disoproxil fumarate (coded units).

Source	DF	Seq SS	Adj SS	Adj MS	F	P
Main Effects	2	11.0900	11.0900	5.5450	201.64	0.000
column	1	11.0450	11.0450	11.0450	401.64	0.000
% organic phase	1	0.0450	0.0450	0.0450	1.64	0.270
2-Way Interactions	1	0.0800	0.0800	0.0800	2.91	0.163

column*solvent	1	0.0800	0.0800	0.0800	2.91	0.163
Residual Error	4	0.1100	0.1100	0.0275		
Pure Error	4	0.1100	0.1100	0.0275		
Total	7	11.2800				

The significant p values were obtained for column and % organic phase. The response of retention time for tenofovir disoproxil fumarate was effected by column and % organic phase.

Table 9: Analysis of Variance for Retention time of dolutegravir (coded units).

Source	DF	Seq SS	Adj SS	Adj MS	F	P
Main Effects	2	14.4625	14.4625	7.2312	175.30	0.000
column	1	13.2612	13.2612	13.2612	321.48	0.000
% organic phase	1	1.2013	1.2013	1.2013	29.12	0.006
2-Way Interactions	1	3.0012	3.0012	3.0012	72.76	0.001
column*solvent	1	3.0012	3.0012	3.0012	72.76	0.001
Residual Error	4	0.1650	0.1650	0.0413		
Pure Error	4	0.1650	0.1650	0.0413		
Total	7	17.6287				

P values obtained were less than 0.05 for the column and % Organic phase. Hence retention time response was dependent on both factors.

3.3. Optimisation of method

From the opti plot column(x- bridge) and % organic phase ratio (70:30) were found to be optimal, based on desirability.

Fig. 5: Opti plot.

Fig. 6: Optimised chromatogram.

3.4. Assay

Table 11: Assay of Lamivudine and Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate and Dolutegravir.

Brand	Drug	Avg sample area (n=5)	Std (µg/ml)	Sample (µg/ml)	Label amount (mg)	Std purity	Amount found (µg/ml)	% assay
-	Dolutegravir	742368	10	10	50	99.9	10.2	99.75
	Lamivudine	2044223	60	60	300	99.9	60.1	99.72
	Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate	1946942	60	60	300	99.9	60.1	99.54

The % assay results were found to be 99.75, 99.72, 99.54 for dolutegravir, lamivudine and tenofovir disoproxil fumarate, respectively. The analysed tablets complies

percentage purity within the acceptable limits as $100\% \pm 10$ as per the ICH guidelines.

Fig. (7): Chromatogram of Assay.

3.5. Method validation

3.5.1 Linearity plots

Fig. 8: Calibration curve for Lamivudine at 250 nm.

Fig. 9: Calibration curve for Dolutegravir at 250 nm.

Fig. 10: Calibration curve for Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate at 250 nm.

Table 12. Results of linearity for Lamivudine, Tenofovir disoproxil Fumarate and Dolutegravir.

S.NO	Dolutegravir		Lamivudine		Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate	
	Conc.(µg/ml)	Peak area	Conc.(µg/ml)	Peak area	Conc.(µg/ml)	Peak area
1	1.00	76689	6.00	214642	6.00	190489
2	2.50	176734	15.00	532381	15.00	586475
3	5.00	376658	30.00	1054869	30.00	974292
4	10.00	748573	60.00	2053049	60.00	1925405
5	12.50	912695	75.00	2610129	75.00	2415511
6	15.00	1111233	90.00	3110621	90.00	2979474
Regression equation	y = 73881.85x + 573.85		y = 34491.34x + 8011.43		y = 32395.62x + 18636.29	
Slope	73881.85		34491.34		32395.62	
Intercept	573.85		8011.43		18636.29	
R²	0.99985		0.99994		0.99923	

The developed analytical method was found linear over the given range of concentration and was examined using linear regression equation showing regression coefficients, 0.9998, 0.9999, 0.9992 and slopes,

73881.85, 34491.34, 32395.62 for dolutegravir, lamivudine and tenofovir disoproxil fumarate respectively.

3.5.2. Accuracy

Table 13: Accuracy results of Dolutegravir by RP-HPLC method.

%Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (mg)	Amount Found (mg)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	370863	5	5.3	100.47	100.52
100%	744651	10	10.1	99.44	
150%	1122864	15	15.7	101.75	

Table 14: The Accuracy results for Lamivudine by RP-HPLC method.

%Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (mg)	Amount Found (mg)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	1012605	30	30.2	100.16	100.57
100%	2041755	60	60.1	99.78	
150%	3065542	90	90.2	100.98	

Table 15: The Accuracy results for Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate by RP-HPLC Method.

%Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (mg)	Amount Found (mg)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	954918	30	30.2	100.77	100.92
100%	1952424	60	60.1	99.68	
150%	2863737	90	90.2	100.16	

The mean percentage recoveries for dolutegravir, lamivudine and tenofovir disoproxil fumarate were determined as 100.52, 100.57, 100.92 and depicts those

were with in the acceptance limits as $100\% \pm 2$ as per the Q2 specifications of ICH guidelines.

Fig. 11: Chromatogram for Accuracy 50%.

Fig. 12: Chromatogram for Accuracy 100%.

Fig. 13: Chromatogram for Accuracy 150%.

3.5.3. Precision

Table 16: Method Precision for Lamivudine and Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate and Dolutegravir by RP-HPLC method.

S. No.	Area for Dolutegravir	Area for Lamivudine	Area for Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate
1	742735	2043598	1949640
2	743895	2011696	1927598
3	748878	2032323	1952467
4	748481	2022357	1957796
5	741365	2021758	1939246
6	743815	2021665	1919763
Average	744862	2024066	1941085
Standard Deviation	3098.705	12173.12	14979.34
%RSD	0.42	0.60	0.77

The % RSD was computed as 0.42, 0.60, 0.77 for dolutegravir, lamivudine and tenofovir disoproxil fumarate respectively & illustrates that they were within the acceptance criteria (≤ 2).

Fig. 14: Chromatogram for Method Precision.

Table 17: Intermediate Precision for Lamivudine and Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate and Dolutegravir by RP-HPLC method.

S. No.	Area for Dolutegravir	Area for Lamivudine	Area for Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate
1	744471	2057759	1927241
2	743722	2041695	1925517
3	745628	2040724	1967192
4	744699	2031596	1932355
5	744816	2041691	1918983
6	749074	2023213	1913152
Average	745402	2039446	1930740
Standard Deviation	1900.601	11595.086	19070.627
%RSD	0.25	0.57	0.99

The % RSD was calculated as 0.25, 0.57, 0.99 for all three drugs were found to be within the acceptance limits (≤ 3) and depicts precision of the method.

Fig. 15: Chromatogram for Intermediate Precision.

3.5.4. Robustness

Table 18: Robustness results of Dolutegravir by RP-HPLC.

Parameter	Dolutegravir					
	Condition	Retention time(min)	Peak area	Resolution	Tailing	Plate count
Flow rate Change(mL/min)	Less flow(0.8ml)	4.699	885281	2.26	1.04	4879
	Actual(1ml)	3.756	743647	3.21	1.01	4845
	More flow(1.2ml)	3.145	543615	2.28	1.05	4792
Organic Phase change	Less Org (45:55)	3.877	834887	2.24	1.05	4893
	Actual(50:50)	3.748	746592	2.28	1.04	4728
	More Org(55:45)	2.71	714246	2.39	1.04	4896

Table 8: Robustness results of Lamivudine by RP-HPLC.

Parameter	Lamivudine					
	Condition	Retention time(min)	Peak area	Resolution	Tailing	Plate count
Flow rate Change (mL/min)	Less flow(0.8ml)	1.887	2255736	12.26	1.05	8979
	Actual(1ml)	1.545	2041658	13.21	1.10	8942
	More flow(1.2ml)	1.286	1462681	12.28	1.05	8979
Organic Phase change	Less Org (45:55)	1.290	2575975	12.24	1.06	8916
	Actual(50:50)	1.532	2016975	14.28	1.03	8984
	More Org(55:45)	1.517	1815046	12.39	1.12	8995

Table 20: Robustness results of Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate by RP-HPLC.

Parameter	Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate					
	Condition	Retention time(min)	Peak area	Resolution	Tailing	Plate count
Flow rate Change(mL/min)	Less flow(0.8ml)	3.897	2176684	2.26	1.11	12579
	Actual(1ml)	3.164	1945782	3.21	1.14	12542
	More flow(1.2ml)	2.616	1412008	2.28	1.05	12579
Organic Phase change	Less Org (45:55)	3.239	2222648	2.24	1.06	12516
	Actual(50:50)	3.140	1903495	2.28	1.03	12584
	More Org(55:45)	2.475	1742291	2.39	1.12	12595

The retention time and plate count were found unaffected with slight deliberate changes in flow rate and mobile phase ratio that represents the robustness of the method.

Fig. (17): Chromatogram for more flow rate (1.2ml).

Fig. (18). Chromatogram for more Organic Phase (55:45).

Fig. (19): Chromatogram for Less Organic (45:55).

3.5.5. LOD and LOQ ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)

Fig. (20): Chromatogram for LOD.

Fig. (21): Chromatogram for LOQ.

Table 21: Sensitivity parameters (LOD & LOQ) by RP-HPLC.

Name of drug	LOD($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	LOQ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
Dolutegravir	0.01	0.1
Lamivudine	0.06	0.6
Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate	0.06	0.6

The LODs were obtained as 0.01, 0.06, 0.06 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, and the LOQs were obtained as 0.1, 0.6, 0.6 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, which indicates the method has good sensitivity.

3.5.6. System suitability

Table 22: System suitability parameters for optimised trial.

S.No	Name	Retention Time	Area	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
1	Dolutegravir	3.785	744791	3.18	1.08	5448
2	Lamivudine	1.529	2036345	43.22	1.05	4154
3	Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate	3.140	1942634	41.13	1.08	4098

The retention time was less than 4 minutes, and plate count NMT 10,000 was observed for all three drugs. The acceptance criteria were $\pm 2\%$ for the per cent coefficient

of variation for the peak area, retention time of the drug, USP plate count.

3.6. Degradation studies

Fig. (22). Chromatogram of Acid degradation.

Fig. (23). Chromatogram of Alkali degradation.

Fig. (24). Chromatogram of Thermal degradation.

Fig. (25). Chromatogram of Peroxide degradation.

CONCLUSION

A simple, accurate, and reproducible HPLC method was developed to determine dolutegravir, lamivudine and tenofovir disoproxil fumarate based on a QbD approach using Design Expert® software, Minitab version(16.2.3).

The optimised conditions were analyzed for thrice, and the developed method was validated as per ICH guidelines, and the results obtained were within the limits. The degradation studies were also performed for the drug by using various stress conditions, and no

degradation products were found in acidic, basic, and oxidative conditions.

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